

Note on an Electrolytic Method of Preparing Silver Oxide.

By M. RAMAN NAYAR AND P. S. MACMAHON.

While conducting experiments on Kohlschütter's (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1908, 14, 49) method of preparing silver hydrosol it was felt that silver oxide prepared chemically by precipitation of silver nitrate with sodium hydroxide was possibly contaminated by adsorbed impurities not easily removable by washing. An unobjectionable method of preparing the oxide free from all electrolytes was desirable, especially in view of the theory advanced by Pauli and co-workers, that a small amount of electrolyte is necessary for the preparation of silver hydrosol.

Such a method is furnished by conducting the electrolysis between silver electrodes in conductivity water as in Bredig's preparation of silver hydrosols. We have been using this method since 1925 for the preparation of silver oxide free from all electrolytes (*Proc. Indian Soc. Congress, Lahore, 1927, p. 171.*). The oxidation of silver anode under such conditions was first noticed by Morse (*Proc. Amer. Acad.*, 1910). Recently a paper has also appeared by Best and Cox (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, p. 2727) who found that the electrolyte produced in the Bredig method of sparking is essentially silver hydroxide. But we do not know of any one having employed this method for preparation of silver oxide.

Pure silver electrodes are dipped in conductivity water $K=1.2 \times 10^{-6}$ in a silica beaker and an arc struck for a minute or two, when enough silver oxide is produced to make the water fairly conducting; the electrodes are then separated 2-3 mm. and electrolysis continued. With 220 volts the current rises nearly to 1 amp. in a few minutes. The anode gets deposited with a dark brown coating of oxide and the cathode with grey spongy silver. No peroxide was detected. Shining films of silver float on the surface of the liquid and tiny sparks are often produced on the surface of films. The liquid gets heated and may even be boiling. The products can be easily scraped from the electrode by a rod of silica or silver and fall to the bottom of the

vessel. The substance is not pure silver oxide but a mixture of silver oxide and silver of varying composition. Under the ordinary conditions obtaining in preparation of Bredig's silver sol the analysis of the products gave the following results in two samples:—

	I,	II,
Ag ₂ O	 01'66 per cent.	57'69 per cent.
Ag	 38'34 per cent.	42'31 per cent.

As previously stated this product is free from all contamination of electrolytes which may be expected in the chemical method of preparation.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF LUCKNOW.

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DR. QUASIM ALI MANSURI, M.A., M.Sc., Ph.D.

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1861—1930

